

Estimation of congestion component of LMP using only local measurements for flexibility markets

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Abstract

Locational marginal prices (LMP) are the dual variables associated with the power balance constraint of the optimal power flow (OPF) problem. Prior works on LMP calculation and forecasting shows that LMP is composed of generation cost, marginal loss cost and distribution network (DN) congestion cost. The focus of this work is to estimate the congestion component of LMP for radial DNs with only local parameter measurements. The true congestion component of LMP is derived by solving an OPF without penalizing the DN loss or generation cost. The estimated component of the LMP, referred to as the flexibility activation signal (FAS), is derived as a function of the nodal voltage profile at the point of common coupling (PCC) and the line loading of incoming and outgoing branches from PCC. The estimated and true congestion components of LMP for all nodes are analyzed via time series analysis using Granger causality and sensitivity and specificity of estimation output. Numerical case studies provide statistical evidence that voltage time series can be utilized to estimate congestion component of DN OPF. Further, we also show that with local parameter measurements such as line loading and/or voltage measurements can accurately estimate DN congestion incidents with an accuracy exceeding 95%. Although, localized congestion estimation is not entirely accurate, however, such a method is privacy-preserving, desired for autonomous operation without the need for centralized communication. Thus, proposed decentralized FAS estimation is inherently cyber-secure and resilient to external attacks, while mitigating DN congestion.

Keywords

Locational marginal price (LMP), statistical analysis, distribution network (DN), flexibility activation signal (FAS).

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This work is supported by the H2020 EUniversal project, grant ID: 864334 (<https://euniversal.eu/>) and the Flemish Government and Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship (VLAIO) through the Moonshot project InduFlexControl (HBC.2019.0113) and project IMPROcap.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Locational marginal prices (LMP) for generation dispatch and congestion mitigation have been in use in meshed transmission networks for more than the last three decades. However, with evolving load patterns of small prosumers, large scale penetration of distributed renewable energy sources and decades of minimal upgrade in distribution networks (DN), congestion mitigation is becoming crucial for DSO operated distribution networks. LMPs are a crucial component in the implementation of local electricity markets, especially in the context of citizen energy communities. The use case of LMP encompasses a pricing mechanism used in electricity markets to signal the value of electricity at specific locations in the power system. It is the marginal cost of supplying the next increment of electric energy at a specific bus while considering the marginal cost of generation and physical aspects of the power system infrastructure [1]. In the context of DN flexibility, LMP signals the value of flexibility services at different locations in the DN. These signals incentivize market participants, such as distributed energy resource (DER) owners, to provide flexibility services, such as demand response, energy storage, or renewable curtailment, in locations where the LMP is high. The LMP can be used as a market-based signal to encourage the deployment of DERs in locations where they can provide the most value to the distribution system and the overall power system.

A. Literature review

The common way of calculating LMP involves solving an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) in a known network based on the load forecast. In [2], LMP prices are calculated for active and reactive power using linear power flow and linear OPF. In [3], LMP is calculated a day ahead to avoid congestion from the EV charging based on the charging schedules of the EV aggregators. A two-stage market clearing mechanism based on LMP for a DN with high DER is presented in [4]. In [5], the full unbalanced AC-OPF based LMP is used to enhance the reliability of the operation in a DN with high DER, battery storage and flexible load. Overall, the literature suggests that distribution LMP can be an effective tool for incentivizing flexible loads to participate in DN flexibility and improve system efficiency, reliability, and stability. In [6], it is shown that the LMP calculation has to be done with full AC formulation despite the higher computation time and the possibility of non-converging solutions. Cubic AC OPF is presented as a more accurate backup to full AC OPF compared to quadratic AC-OPF, linear AC-OPF, or DC-OPF. A decentralized method for overvoltage mitigation was proposed in [7], where the droop curve is used to mitigate congestion due to high RES. In [8], the droop curve based on sensitivity is used to activate the flexible resources in the system to mitigate the congestion while still using the centralized OPF for accessing flexibility needs.

B. Motivation and contribution

From the literature review, it is seen that the usual LMP is being used for market clearing based on the day-ahead forecast. Furthermore, relaxed OPF is usually used to reduce computational effort. Alternatively, droop-based pricing is in use to activate flexible resources. However, both case requires running an OPF or computing sensitivity matrix based on historical data. In this paper, we propose to present an equivalent of the congestion component of LMP based on local measurements, which can be used as a signal to activate flexible resources. By doing so, the necessity of OPF or sensitivity matrices is eliminated. The key contributions of this paper are:

- The estimated congestion component of LMP is referred to as the flexibility activation signal (FAS). We present 3 models for generating decentralized FAS, as shown in Fig. 1,
- Using Granger causality, we show that voltage measurement can be used to estimate the OPF duals associated with the congestion component, and
- Localized parameters can fairly accurately detect a congestion incident. Numerical results indicate that voltage or line loading measurement can estimate $\geq 95\%$ of congestion incidents.

Fig. 1: Proposed decentralized FAS generation architecture [9] using only local measurements and no centralized feedback.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we present the OPF model for generating only the congestion component of LMP. Section III details the models for generating FAS and the performance indices used for evaluating the numerical case studies detailed in Section IV. Section V concludes the paper.

II. CONGESTION COMPONENT FOR LMP

LMP calculation requires a formulation of OPF, which could be simplified DC or full AC. In this section, we discuss the LMP using full AC OPF:

$$\text{Min } \left\{ \sum c_{gi} P_{gi} + \lambda^L \times (\text{Losses}) \right\}$$

subject to,

$$V_{\min} \leq V_i \leq V_{\max}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (1)$$

$$S_{ij} < S_{ij}^{\max}, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (2)$$

$$P_{gi} - P_{di} - P(V, \theta) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \forall g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (3)$$

$$Q_{gi} - Q_{di} - Q(V, \theta) = 0 \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, d \in \mathcal{D}, g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{gi}^{\min} \leq P_{gi} \leq P_{gi}^{\max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{gi}^{\min} \leq Q_{gi} \leq Q_{gi}^{\max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, g \in \mathcal{G} \quad (6)$$

$$\angle(V_i V_j^*) \in [\theta_{ij}^{\min}, \theta_{ij}^{\max}], \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (7)$$

where: c_{gi} is cost of generator gi

P_{gi}, Q_{gi} are active and reactive output of gi

P_{di}, Q_{di} are active and reactive demand of load di

V_{\min}, V_{\max} are lower and upper limit of voltages at node i

S_{ij}, S_{ij}^{\max} are line flow and its maximum value in line ij

LMP (λ_i) of the above formulation are the Lagrange multipliers of (3) and are formed by three components:

- a) energy price at the slack bus (λ),
- b) marginal congestion cost (λ^C), and
- c) cost of marginal loss (λ^L) [10]

and is usually represented as the sum of them as follows:

$$\lambda_i = \lambda - \underbrace{\frac{\partial \text{Loss}}{\partial P_i \lambda}}_{\lambda^L} + \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^K T_{ik} \mu_k}_{\lambda^C} \quad (8)$$

The details of these calculations are skipped in this paper and interested readers are pointed to [11]. For cost-effective transmission system operation, all three components play a vital role as:

- 1) meshed operation means the same load can be fed from two different directions,

- 2) network has well-equipped measurement devices and communication network,
- 3) due to the bulk power, the economic operation comes with less cost.

While dealing with the DN, which is usually radial, has no communication infrastructure, limited measurement devices, and deals with a comparably less amount of power, computing all three components in a centralized way is not an economical option. Furthermore, if the objective of the DN operator is to reduce local congestion, the interest will remain only on the congestion component of the LMP, i.e. λ^C . This cost depends upon the T_{ik} , the power flow sensitivity to the injection node i with respect to a slack reference, and μ is the shadow price vector for the line constraints. Calculating these components requires a full AC OPF solution based on the real-time injection profiles. Since, the congestion component is independent of the cost of losses and generation cost, therefore, in the AC OPF problem solved, we *do not penalize generation cost or the losses* in the objective function.

III. LMP CONGESTION COMPONENT ESTIMATION WITH PERFORMANCE INDICES

In this section, we detail the framework for generating a FAS for congestion mitigation. This signal is derived using local measurements at the PCC voltage magnitude and the line loading percentages for the lines connecting a consumer. The design of FAS was first introduced in prior works [8], [12]–[14]. In this work, we focus on calculating FAS with local measurements and statistically quantifying the similarities between the OPF duals denoting the congestion component derived in Section 2. In Section III-A, we detail the three models used for LMP estimation based on different parameters measured. In Section III-B, the performance metrics are detailed that are used for evaluating the numerical results.

A. Models for FAS calculation

The nomenclature used to refer to the estimated OPF congestion component is referred to as flexibility activation signal (FAS) because this estimated signal can be used for activating flexibility resources for mitigating DN congestion. Next, three FAS models are presented. These models are a function of the locally measured parameters. Distribution network congestion incidents (DNCI)¹ in low voltage grids is a local problem that is often reflected in locally measured parameters such as (i) PCC voltage, and (ii) line loading. Of course, there are limitations associated with the decentralized estimation of the congestion component of OPF dual, such as (a) congestion in the intermediate part of the grid with no measurement feedback cannot be detected accurately, (b) propagation of dual variables in a network. The latter refers to the nonzero dual variable values for nodes with no local violation but DNCI somewhere else in the network, possibly in the same radial DN feeder. Although this shortcoming of decentralized FAS generation cannot emulate the OPF duals associated with congestion, we show that by using the drooping structure of FAS design, these shortcomings can be reduced substantially. Further, decentralized FAS generation would *eliminate the need for communication infrastructure*, which not only is expensive but also prone to cyberattacks due to information distortion by potential attackers. Next, we detail the proposed FAS models.

Fig. 2: FAS design based on Model 1. x -axis denotes voltage magnitude and y -axis is the FAS value based on model 1.

¹Distribution network congestion incidents (considered in this paper) are composed of: (a) line overloading, and (b) voltage violations at nodes.

1) *Model 1: Only voltage measurement:* Many smart meters already measure the voltage magnitude at PCC. Prior works such as [15], [16] show that voltage violations precede line loading limit violations. Thus, voltage magnitude is a strong indicator of DN congestion. The voltage in DN under healthy operation should be bounded with V_{\min} and V_{\max} , which are the operational limits set by the system operator. The presented model is motivated by Volt-Watt inverter control for controlling active power. The permissible level is denoted as Δ_{perm} . Based on FAS model 1 presented in Fig. 2, for voltage levels with $[1 - \Delta_{\text{perm}}, 1 + \Delta_{\text{perm}}]$, the FAS remains zero. For voltage magnitudes outside this range, the FAS is nonzero. The orange shaded region incentivizes load curtailment and the green region incentivizes generation curtailment. The saturating levels denoted as $VC_{i,P}^{\max}$ are a function of the nodal voltage sensitivity.

2) *Model 2: Only line loading measurement:* The LMP variables are associated with nodes of the DN. However, line loading is associated with branches in a DN. Here, we improve on the line loading projection mechanism compared to prior works [8], [12], [13]. Fig. 3 shows model 2 for FAS generation. The thermal line loading of the branches connected to PCC will require additional sensors, as they are not measured by the smart meters presently used.

Projection mechanism: Instead of weighted normalization of line loading projected onto the nodes, we assign the worst-case line loading onto the nodes. Model 2 considers the nodal projected line loading. The projected thermal component of FAS is non-zero if projected line loading exceeds a preset threshold of ΔT_{perm} or drops below $-\Delta T_{\text{perm}}$. Detail of the projection mechanism is summarized in Appendix B.

Fig. 3: FAS design based on Model 2. x -axis denotes nodal projected line loading and y -axis is the FAS value based on model 2.

3) *Model 3: Measuring voltage and line loading magnitude:* The last model considers both nodal projected line loading and the voltage magnitude at PCC. The FAS design based on Model 3 is mathematically described in Equation 5 of [13].

B. Performance indices

The goal of the numerical experiments is to answer the following questions:

- Can we forecast dual variables using voltage and/or line loading information?
 - Is there any statistical evidence to support this claim?
- Qualitative comments on the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of model 1 to 3 estimated FAS and the OPF dual associated with the congestion component?

In order to answer the above questions, we use the following three statistical tools.

1) *Granger causality test (GCT)*: Granger causality is a statistical concept that determines whether one time series data can help in predicting the other time series. In our application of GCT, the delay is zero, as the dual variables at a particular time is only governed by the network state in that instant. In other words, our system of analysis is assumed to be memoryless. Interested readers can explore more on GCT here [17].

2) *Level of significance*: Statistical significance indicate whether an observed relationship in time series data sheet or effect on variables is likely to be genuine or simply a matter of chance. The level of significance is measured using p -value. Typically, in statistics, p -value of less than 5% is assumed to be significant. Of course, p -value can vary in different fields. In domains such as medical science, pharmacology, astronomy, a substantially small p -value is used.

3) *Accuracy, Sensitivity and Specificity*: For our present work, the comparison of estimated FAS and dual variable (λ^C) can lead to four possible outcomes:

- True positive (TP): the dual and estimated FAS are simultaneously non-zero, implying accurate detection of nodal congestion.

$$\text{TP} = \sum_t \sum_n \mathbb{1}(|\lambda_{t,n}^C| \geq \beta \ \& \ |\text{FAS}_{t,n}| \geq \beta) \ \forall t, \forall n, \quad (9)$$

where t and n denotes the time and node id. β is the threshold of significance.

- False positive (FP): the dual variable is zero, but FAS is non-zero. This situation occurs due to the droop structure of FAS generation used for Model 1 to 3.

$$\text{FP} = \sum_t \sum_n \mathbb{1}(|\lambda_{t,n}^C| < \beta \ \& \ |\text{FAS}_{t,n}| \geq \beta) \ \forall t, \forall n, \quad (10)$$

- True negative (TN): the dual and estimated FAS are simultaneously zero, implying no congestion.

$$\text{TN} = \sum_t \sum_n \mathbb{1}(|\lambda_{t,n}^C| < \beta \ \& \ |\text{FAS}_{t,n}| < \beta) \ \forall t, \forall n, \quad (11)$$

- False negative (FN): there is congestion in DN (i.e. dual variable is non-zero) but the estimated FAS is zero. In such a case, the estimation misses the congestion event.

$$\text{FN} = \sum_t \sum_n \mathbb{1}(|\lambda_{t,n}^C| \geq \beta \ \& \ |\text{FAS}_{t,n}| < \beta) \ \forall t, \forall n, \quad (12)$$

This is the case where FAS misses identifying a DNICs. Note (9), (10), (11), (12) used indicator functions and do compare the shape of true and estimated time series.

Using the above cases, following metrics are used:

$$\text{accuracy} = 100 \times \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + TN + FP + FN)}, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{sensitivity} = 100 \times \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{specificity} = 100 \times \frac{TN}{(TN + FP)}. \quad (15)$$

IV. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATION

The numerical example uses an adaptation of a Spanish DN with 76 nodes, 75 branches and 52 loads connected to 28 nodes. This test example uses a single-phase equivalent DN model. More network details can be found in [14], [18]. The network details and associated load profiles are made open source for reproducibility of our research [19]. Synthetic data is generated for 1000 scenarios for 24 hours (hourly sampled) load profiles by power flow and OPF dual variables are accumulated using PowerModels.jl in Julia / JuMP [20]. The voltage limits for this DN are assumed to be $V_{\min} = 0.92$, $V_{\max} = 1.08$. The network layout is shown in Appendix A.

A. Case study 1: Comparing measurements with congestion component of OPF duals

Note that although the voltage is violated for nodes 46 to 50 (not shown in the paper) and thermal overload is observed in branch 64, we see the impact in dual variable plotted for node 20 in Fig. 4, where no congestion is observed. This implies the dual variables are affected by congestion observed in different nodes in the test network. Thus, we can conclude that the OPF dual variables associated with DN congestion are affected by DNCIs occurring at the different parts of the DN. Such an effect is hard to predict with only local measurements. For these reasons, we set $\Delta_{\text{perm}} = 0.45$, $\Delta T_{\text{perm}} = 85\%$. Note that by setting these permissible limits, the model 1 FAS generated estimates the OPF dual shown in Fig. 4(a) fairly well. For Fig. 4, a Pearson correlation is performed to test if there is a relationship between nodal voltage and dual variable for active power. The results of the Pearson correlation indicated that there was a statistically significant positive association between dual and voltage time series, with a correlation of 65.4% and p -value of 0.0005.

Fig. 11 (in Appendix C) shows the metrics for the GCT test performed over one of the scenarios. Time series inputs for the GCT test are the voltage and dual variable time series. Note that the GCT test output of 1 indicates that the dual variable time series can be forecasted using the voltage time series. Note that for some nodes, the p -value is more than 0.05 therefore, statistical significance is not guaranteed. However, from Fig. 11(b), the p -value remains close to this threshold of 0.05, indicating causality. The test statistics remain close to 3.5 for all nodes.

It is observed that for scenarios with no congestion, the GCT test performed worse. For these reasons, we discard the ≈ 300 scenarios for obtaining the distribution of p -value, as for these scenarios, the dual variable remains zero. The distribution of the sum of the absolute value of dual variables is shown in Fig. 5. Using the remaining scenarios, we obtain Fig. 6. Note that the median of the nodal p -value distribution of each node lies very close to the level of statistical significance. Thus, we can state that voltage time series can be used for estimating the dual variables associated with the congestion component.

A similar observation was not made for the GCT test for the thermal line loading and λ^C .

Fig. 4: The dual variable, voltage time series and the model 1 estimate of the dual.

Fig. 5: Scenario's histogram based on the sum of the absolute value of dual variables

Fig. 6: Distribution of p -value for scenarios with DN congestions

Fig. 7: Accuracy of Model 1, 2 and 3 in %

B. Case study 2: How accurate is the estimation?

In this case study, we provide comments on the quality of estimation. Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show the accuracy and type 1 error² plots. Note that the x-axis shows the threshold of the magnitude comparison. For any level, x , it is TP only if the estimated FAS and the OPF dual exceed this level. From Fig. 7, the estimation accuracy for Model 3 surpasses Models 1 and 2. However, voltage measurement only leads to better estimation accuracy compared to line loading measurement. Fig. 8 shows that as the threshold increases, the FP level is decreasing. The FP is substantial due to the droop-based design of FAS for models 1 to 3.

Table I lists performance metrics for comparing three models. Model 2 outperforms others for sensitivity, specificity, and type 1 error, while model 3 performs the best for accuracy percentage.

Using this case study, we have established the effectiveness of models 1, 2 and 3 in estimating the

²Type 1 error refers to the ratio of false positive instances over all instances

Fig. 8: Type 1 error

TABLE I: Statistical metrics for $\beta = 0.02$

%	Sensitivity	Specificity	Type 1 error	Accuracy
Model 1	38.95	96.37	3.61	97.47
Model 2	2.0	99.12	0.85	96.04
Model 3	39.99	95.53	4.48	97.49

congestion component of the OPF duals. The estimation accuracy for all these models exceeds 96%, which is very promising for applying them in a decentralized manner. The decentralized estimation of FSP would assist in activating flexibility resources without the need for installing communication infrastructure. Note the FSP can only be used for local congestion mitigation. For services such as redispatch, services for transmission system operator communication infrastructure would still be irreplaceable. However, decentralized congestion mitigation can be performed in a standalone manner. A critical question to answer is to select the permissible range of operation. Consider the permissible range is denoted as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{\text{perm}+} &= \Delta_{\text{fac}}(V_{\text{max}} - 1), \quad \Delta_{\text{perm}-} = \Delta_{\text{fac}}(1 - V_{\text{min}}), \\ \Delta_{\text{perm}}^{T+} &= \Delta_{\text{fac}} \times 100, \quad \Delta_{\text{perm}}^{T-} = \Delta_{\text{fac}} \times (-100). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

For permissible ranges calculated using (16), the variability in false positive and accuracy of method 1 is given in Fig. 9. Note that for a narrower permissible range, the share of FP cases is very high. For $\Delta_{\text{fac}} = 0$, the share of FP exceeds 80% while the accuracy of estimating TP and TN is below 20%. This implies that by controlling the width of permissible ranges, the sensitivity of the generated FAS signal can be controlled.

Further work is needed to develop a mechanism for tuning these ranges, which would be governed by network topology, load profiles etc.

Fig. 9: The trade-off for selecting a wider permissible range for method 1.

V. CONCLUSION

We proposed models for generating flexibility activation signal (FAS) using voltage and/or nodal projected thermal line loading. Since FAS is generated using only local measurements, no additional communication and remote control overhead is needed. Statistically, we verify that these decentralized FAS are positively associated with OPF dual variables corresponding to the congestion component (λ^C) of the locational marginal prices. We show that FAS can accurately estimate more than 96% of the congestion incidents. The congestion incidents refer to the non-zero value of the modified OPF duals. For only voltage measurement, the accuracy exceeds 97.4%. We also establish the statistical significance of using voltage time series for estimating these dual variables using the Granger causality test, validated for 1000 scenarios with 24 hours time series data.

In future works, we will focus on understanding the impact of dual propagation to nodes with no network violation. Further work is also needed to create a framework to select the permissible limits for locally measured parameters and tuning the levels of the thresholds, which will be governed by the network topology, load and renewable energy distribution in the DN. Finally, further studies are needed to extend this work for the three-phase unbalanced DN, where current and voltage unbalances will also contribute to FAS calculations.

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APPENDIX

A. Network diagram

Fig. 10: Network diagram for the 76 bus Spanish DN. The substation is indicated with the blue circle.

B. Branch loading projection onto nodes

In this paper, we improve the projection mechanism proposed in earlier work [12]. The first step in this direction is to identify the flow direction based on the convention used. In the case of radial DN, this convention is assumed to be the power flow from the substation to the prosumers. Consider $b_{y,z,t}$ denotes a branch connecting node y to z . The flow direction is identified using nodal voltage magnitudes as

$$\zeta_{b_{y,z}}^t = \mathbb{1}(V_{y,t} \geq V_{z,t}) - \mathbb{1}(V_{z,t} > V_{y,t}). \quad (17)$$

If there is a reverse power flow, i.e., DGs generate more power than the power consumed by connected loads, the value of $\zeta = -1$ for that branch. Some nodes may be connected to more than one branch, for which the

nodal projection is denoted as the *maximum* magnitude of the product of the flow convention and the line loading in percentage.

C. Additional numerical results

Fig. 11: Granger causality test